

Conference Abstract

Openprobe: a frugal multiparameter probe for marine and continental waters monitoring

Vincent Raimbault[‡], Raul Sanchez Olvera[‡]

[‡] LAAS CNRS, Toulouse, France

Corresponding author: Vincent Raimbault (vincent.raimbault@laas.fr)

Received: 25 Feb 2025 | Published: 28 May 2025

Citation: Raimbault V, Sanchez Olvera R (2025) Openprobe: a frugal multiparameter probe for marine and continental waters monitoring. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e151405. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e151405>

Abstract

Aquatic ecosystems need accurate observation to understand its trajectory in a context of increasing anthropogenic pressure and climate change. These environments are however undersampled in many areas (Brewin et al. 2017, Kirchner et al. 2004): acquiring essential variables at relevant spatial and temporal resolution is often not compatible with traditional methods of sample collection followed by laboratory analysis, but field-deployable or in-situ systems are either too expensive, too complicated to be used by non-trained users or even non-existent. In an effort to propose an alternative in-situ measurement system for biogeochemical and physicochemical measurement in marine and continental waters, we developed a multiparameter probe that measures 7 parameters for a very modest bill-of-materials cost (around 300 € for a single prototype). The performance of this probe is sufficient for most water bodies, both in terms of range and sensitivity, and its replication is facilitated by the use of rapid-prototyping methods.

The Openprobe multiparameter (Fig. 1) is able to measure conductivity, temperature, pressure (depth or water level above), dissolved oxygen, turbidity, chlorophyll a, photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) as well as water color. These parameters were chosen based on a compromise between their relevance and our capability to measure them at a scientifically appropriate standard using low-cost components, an approach which resonates with the definition of the Standard Observations in eLTER (Zacharias et al. 2021).

Figure 1. [doi](#)

Picture of the Openprobe multiparameter sonde from the optical sensors side. The chlorophyll a fluorometer filters are visible in blue (excitation) and red (emission), while the cyan light indicates the oxygen optode. Key performance for these optical sensors is given as a reference.

The electronic architecture is based around an Adafruit Feather M0 microcontroller board, an Adafruit Adalogger microSD-card logger with a Real-Time-Clock, and two custom Printed Circuit Boards (PCBs) that hosts the different sensors. Housing of the probe uses a Blue Robotics 2" diameter enclosure tubes. The sensor's PCBs are integrated in end-caps fabricated by stereolithography (SLA), using a desktop Formlabs Form 3 SLA printer with Black V4 resin. Compared to conventional fused-deposition modelling 3D printing (FDM), SLA is an isotropic printing technique which delivers fully dense and watertight parts. The higher resolution of SLA also allows to create o-ring grooves with appropriate tolerance, and has shown to be a valid fabrication technique even for the challenging pressures encountered in deep-sea science (Karp et al. 2023, Phillips et al. 2019). Atop of that, the 3D printed end-cads ensures auto-alignment of the optical elements (LEDs, photodiodes) and optical filters. The assembly/disassembly can be done manually without any tool, for easy access to the electronics, the battery, or the micro SD card on the field. Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), a silicone-based material with good transparency in the VIS-IR, is used within the end-caps to create optical ports, and also acts similarly to a potting material to ensure watertightness.

The first PCB is integrated at the top of the probe, and contains the CTD (Conductivity, Depth, Temperature) as well as the PAR sensor. The conductivity sensor is based around a two-electrode cell on a ceramic substrate connected to an impedance analyzer integrated circuit (IC). Intercomparison with a Decagon CTD-10 and an Atlas Scientific EZO sensor showed that our sensor offered a better sensitivity, together with a smaller cost and a lower power consumption. Pressure and temperature sensors are based around the same IC used by Blue Robotics pressure and temperature sensors, and as such as been validated in many conditions (Poulsen et al. 2022). We worked on their

integration on a custom PCB, with special care taken in minimizing the thermal inertia around the temperature sensor to reduce its response time when performing profiling analysis. The PAR sensor completes this part of the probe. It is based around the AMS AS7341, modified with a diffuser cut precisely with the xurography technique (Bartholomeusz et al. 2005), and intercompares with a $\pm 5\%$ confidence interval versus an Apogee SQ-512-SS sensor (Fig. 2), a value commonly exceeded when comparing different commercial sensors (Long et al. 2012).

Figure 2. [doi](#)

Intercomparison between an Apogee SQ-512-SS PAR sensor, and the modified AS7341 used in the Openprobe.

The second PCB, located at the opposite end of the probe, contains a chlorophyll a fluorometer, an oxygen optode, and a turbidity sensor. The chlorophyll a fluorometer uses synchronous detection: this approach allows efficient ambient light rejection, and captures the weak fluorescence signals observed due to the small fluorescence yield of *in-vivo* chl.a (Morrison 2003). The oxygen optode uses PreSens Pst3 oxygen sensor spots, paired with a custom optoelectronic readout architecture. A DDS (Direct Digital Synthesizer) generates a sine wave to excite the Pst3 luminophore, and an I/Q demodulator measures the phase shift between excitation and the emitted fluorescence. The fluorescence signal is quenched in the presence of oxygen, which translates to a decrease of the fluorescence decay and *in-fine* by a phase shift. This is similar to the operating principle of Aanderaa optodes, commonly found in the Biogeochemical Argo floats. Our optode is intercompared with a benchtop PreSens Fibox 4 system and shown good accuracy (Fig. 3). Finally, the turbidity sensor implements 90° nephelometry as well as 180° backscattering measurements to cover a broad range of turbidity. Its architecture is based around an Analog Devices ADPD1080, an IC usually found in smartwatches for the measurement of photoplethysmography (PPG).

Figure 3. [doi](#)

Illustration of the performance of the oxygen optode developed for the Openprobe multiparameter probe, with an intercomparison between a PReSens Fibox 4 benchtop equipment and our sensor. Both sensors are simultaneously immersed in a vial saturated in oxygen, and nitrogen is then bubbled in the solution to reduce oxygen concentration over time.

The Openprobe multiparameter probe could be a very valuable tool in order to increase spatial and temporal resolution in aquatic ecosystem monitoring. Through the use of advanced, yet affordable electronic components initially developed for the Internet Of Things market, we created a frugal tool without compromising on accuracy.

Keywords

in-situ sensors, frugal, multiparameter probe, conductivity, depth, temperature, chlorophyll a, turbidity, dissolved oxygen, PAR, water color

Presenting author

Vincent Raimbault

Presented at

ORAL

Funding program

This work received financial support from the state managed by the National Agency for Research under the Future Investment Program integrated into France 2030, with reference ANR-21-ESRE-0014.

Grant title

TERRA FORMA ANR21-ESRE-0014

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Bartholomeusz DA, Boute RW, Andrade JD, et al. (2005) Xurography: rapid prototyping of microstructures using a cutting plotter. *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems* 14 (6): 1364-1374. <https://doi.org/10.1109/jmems.2005.859087>
- Brewin RW, Hyder K, Andersson A, Billson O, Bresnahan P, Brewin T, Cyronak T, Dall'Olmo G, de Mora L, Graham G, Jackson T, Raitsos D, et al. (2017) Expanding Aquatic Observations through Recreation. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 4 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00351>
- Karp MA, Phillips B, Edie SM, et al. (2023) Investigations into 3D-printed nautiloid-inspired pressure housings. *Bioinspiration & Biomimetics* 18 (6). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-3190/acfeb8>
- Kirchner J, Feng X, Neal C, Robson A, et al. (2004) The fine structure of water-quality dynamics: the (high-frequency) wave of the future. *Hydrological Processes* 18 (7): 1353-1359. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.5537>
- Long M, Rheuban J, Berg P, Ziemann J, et al. (2012) A comparison and correction of light intensity loggers to photosynthetically active radiation sensors. *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods* 10 (6): 416-424. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lom.2012.10.416>
- Morrison JR, et al. (2003) In situ determination of the quantum yield of phytoplankton chlorophyll a fluorescence: A simple algorithm, observations, and a model. *Limnology and Oceanography* 48 (2): 618-631. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lm.2003.48.2.0618>
- Phillips B, Licht S, Haiat K, Bonney J, Allder J, Chaloux N, Shomberg R, Noyes T, et al. (2019) DEEPI: A miniaturized, robust, and economical camera and computer system for deep-sea exploration. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers* 153 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr.2019.103136>
- Poulsen E, Eggertsen M, Jepsen E, Melvad C, Rysgaard S, et al. (2022) Lightweight drone-deployed autonomous ocean profiler for repeated measurements in hazardous areas – Example from glacier fronts in NE Greenland. *HardwareX* 11 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ohx.2022.e00313>

- Zacharias S, Anttila S, Bäck J, Böttcher K, Mallast U, Mirtl M, Schaub M, Trotsiuk V (2021) Discussion paper on eLTER Standard Observations (eLTER SOs). EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project. Deliverable D3.1.